

VIBRATION EXCITATED LOW-PRESSURE CASTING,
A NEW ROUTE TO PRODUCE METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES.

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the principles and some properties of composites made by a new low-pressure route to produce preform based metal matrix composites.

The problems of getting a preform infiltrated by molten metal are well known. The use of high pressure in combination with high temperature enables infiltration of fibre preforms. However, that kind of approach also often activate chemical attacks, gives some remaining porosity with gases entrapped at high pressure and uncontrolled deformation of the fibre preform.

By the use of low applied pressures, it is possible to avoid the uncontrolled fibre distribution and preform breaks of composites made by conventional high-pressure squeeze casting.

For the use of low applied pressures for infiltration, however, some kind of energy to overcome the geometrical barriers for wetting of the preform is needed. This is done by high energy vibrational assistance of the casting. Thus, temperatures less than 100°C above liquidus can be used for Al-alloys too.

Deformation of preforms less than 1% and very low fractions of porosity are obtained in the composites.

Infiltration front velocity of the molten metal matrix has been detected and registered continuously during casting. Data can best be interpreted in terms of metastable equilibrium models in which an advancing liquid front has to overcome energy barriers associated with geometrical features.

KEYWORDS: Composites ; matrix/aluminium/preform ; manufacturing/vibration/low pressure.

SYMBOLS AND UNITS

μ	viscosity [Pa·s]	u	velocity in x-direction [m·s ⁻¹]
ρ	density [kg·m ⁻³]	v	velocity in y-direction [m·s ⁻¹]
ν	kinematic viscosity [m ² ·s ⁻¹]	w	velocity in z-direction [m·s ⁻¹]
ω	rotation [rad·s ⁻¹]	f	frequency [Hz]
θ_{STAT}, θ_S	static contact angle [deg]	P, p	pressure [Pa]
θ_{DYN}, θ_D	dynamic contact angle [deg]	T'	temperature [K]
∇	operator	m	mass [kg]
t	time [s]	T	period of time (1/f)[s ⁻¹]
L	infiltration path length [m]	A	amplitude of vibration [m]

1. INTRODUCTION

In many cases the introduction of mechanical energy by vibrations into a system gives possibilities of adjusting process parameters [1]. A well known example is vibration of concrete in order to obtain close packing and avoid air inclusions. The coefficient of friction in machining processes can be adjusted by vibrational assistance. In metals casting vibrations are used to avoid segregation during solidification. High frequency vibrations also make undercooling in thin sections possible.

Aluminium is protected by a passivating layer of mixed oxides preventing wetting, but of course breakthroughs and reactions occur if the applied pressure is high enough. [2] The consequence is however high wetting angles and bad infiltration of preforms, unless high pressures or chemical modifications of the alloy or fibres are used. [2-5] High pressures, however, do deform preforms. Chemical modifications to improve wetting also in many cases cause chemical attacks on fibres or embrittlement [2,3].

Contact angles of both wetting and non wetting liquids have been reported to decrease by ultrasonic vibrations [1]. The aim of this work is a parametric study in order to utilize this possibility for composite materials production, here concentrated to aluminium alloy matrix systems.

2. THEORY

Infiltration data are usually interpreted in terms of the metastable equilibrium configuration models in which an advancing liquid front has to overcome energy barriers associated with geometrical features [1]. Spontaneous infiltration is energetically possible if and only if the contact angle θ is less than 90 degrees.

The aim of this study is a demonstration from first principles of fluid mechanics of the possibility to induce infiltration and wetting of molten metal in a fibre preform by vibrational activation and obtain approximate estimates of the frequencies needed for two different mechanisms to work.

Modelling The first case is the contact angle (θ) studied as a function of the frequency of vibrations transmitted by the preform. The path of the infiltration front is modelled as a thin slot between two plane walls. The walls are given the properties of the fibres. This model is studied in terms of a quasistatic equilibrium using the dynamic contact angle (θ_{DYN}) instead of the static (θ_{STAT}). The motion of the fluid due to the vibrational forces is determined by viscosity (μ) and density (ρ).

Molten metal can in most cases be regarded as Newtonian fluids, i.e. with viscosity independent of deformation rate. From the Stoke hypothesis giving the relations of normal stress versus deformation rate and the Navier-Stoke equations, an expression for the motion of the fluid can be obtained [10,11].

Figure 1. The geometrical model of the infiltration front with the distance (R) between the walls and the normal to the fluidsurface in the (x)-direction.

The vector of motion is defined:

$$\vec{c} = u\hat{x} + v\hat{y} + w\hat{z} \quad (1)$$

The movement is assumed to take place in the (x) direction with liquid layers moving parallel to the walls like rigid plates.

$$v = w = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\delta u}{\delta x} = 0 \quad (3)$$

The equation of continuity is then given by

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{c} = 0 \quad (4)$$

The viscosity (μ) and the density (ρ) are assumed to be the same throughout the liquid and introducing the kinematic viscosity (ν):

$$\nu = \frac{\mu}{\rho} \quad (5)$$

The Navier-Stoke equation can be written:

$$\frac{D\vec{c}}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho}\nabla p_z + \nu\nabla^2 \cdot \vec{c} \quad (6)$$

With the use of the assumptions (2) and (3) above, equation (6) can be reduced to:

$$\frac{\delta u}{\delta t} = \nu \frac{\delta^2 u}{\delta y^2} \quad (7)$$

The simultaneously sinusoidal excitation in x -direction of the walls is written in the form

$$u = A\omega[\cos(\omega t + \alpha y) + \cos(\omega t + \alpha(y - R))] \quad (8)$$

with boundary conditions, here assuming full adhesion to the walls:

$$y = R - y = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$u(t, y) = f(y = 0)[\cos(\omega t + \alpha y) + \cos(\omega t + \alpha(y - R))] \quad (10)$$

The analytical solution of the equation (7) gives

$$\alpha = -\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{2\nu}} \quad (11)$$

and the amplitude function

$$f(y) = A\omega \exp(-\alpha y) \quad (12)$$

the position of the surface of the fluid (x) is obtained by integration of the function u(t,y) regarding y

$$x(t, y) = A[\exp(-\alpha y)\sin(\omega t - \alpha y) + \exp(\alpha(y - R))\sin(\omega + \alpha(y - R))] \quad (13)$$

The contact angle between the fluid and the wall can be regarded as the dynamic angle of wetting (θ_{DYN}) and is given by

$$\theta_{DYN} = \left(\frac{\delta x}{\delta y}\right)_{t,y=0} \quad (14)$$

If the velocity (u) is known we can easily get the acceleration by derivation regarding to (t). Now we can write the total kinematic pressure (P) acting in (x)-direction as a function of time:

$$P = \frac{\rho \cdot L}{R} \int_0^R \frac{\delta u}{\delta t}(y) dy \quad (15)$$

Simulation of the infiltration process The viscosity of a molten metal is a function of thermally activated processes and thus [6]

$$\mu(T) = \mu_0 \exp\left(\frac{E}{RT}\right) \quad (16)$$

For the Al-alloy / Saffil Al_2O_3 system of this work

Figure 2. Viscosity $\mu(T)$ [Pa·s], Al-alloy Al11Si [6]

The density of Al11Si is:

$$\rho = 2800 \text{ [kg/m}^3\text{]}$$

The width (R) of the channels in a Saffil preform exhibit considerable variation and thus the simulation is done for different magnitude of order in the range $R=1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ to $1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ [m]. The average diameter of the fibres is approximately $3 \cdot 10^{-6}$ [m].

As an reference to the calculated dynamic contact angles (θ_{DYN}) the static contact angle of Al on Al_2O_3 can according to [7] be written as a linear function:

$$\theta_{STAT} = 103 - 0.05(T - T_m)[deg] \quad (17)$$

There are however discrepancies between the results of the contact angle studies reported by different groups, probably due to different atmosphere, purity and substrate.

3. RESULTS THEORETICAL STUDY

With the use of equations (13)-(15) and the given data, some effects of vibrational assistance on the parameters of casting have been simulated for a melt close to liquidus. Amplitude level (A) of the vibrational excitation is determined by experimental equipment. Surface behaviour during excitation and variation of (θ_{DYN}).

Figure 3. Effects of the momentum of inertia of the melt subjected to vibrational forces of amplitude $A=1\cdot 10^{-4}$ m and frequency a) $f=1$ kHz and b) $f=10$ kHz. The different lines represent movement of the surface during 1 period of time, in steps of $1/8$ period.

Figure 4. The dynamic contact angle (θ_{DYN}) during one period ($t=f^{-1}$) of time for $f=10$ kHz at the amplitude $A=1\cdot 10^{-4}$ m for different width of the slot in the range $R=1\cdot 10^{-3}$ m to $R=1\cdot 10^{-6}$ m.

Figure 5. The dynamic contact angle (θ_{DYN}) during one period ($t=f^{-1}$) of time for $f= 50$ kHz and other conditions as figure (4)

Temperature influence on the dynamic contact angle (θ_{DYN}).

Figure 6. The dynamic contact angle (θ_{DYN}) at 850K and 1000K, $f= 10$ kHz, $A= 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m, $R= 1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m.

The total kinematic pressure and a phase study of (P) and (θ_{DYN}).

Figure 7. Maximum total kinematic pressure as a function of the slot width (R) for different frequencies (f), $L = 1$ m.

Figure 8. Phase relation between θ_{DYN} and total kinematic pressure (P). $f = 10$ kHz and a) $R = 1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m, b) $R = 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m.

4. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Basic experimental work is done verifying the theory of vibration excited low-pressure casting of Al/Saffil Al_2O_3 shortfibre preform composite material.

Initial tests Infiltration of Saffil preforms by the use of vibrational excitation and a low pressure is done with the following equipment. The aluminium (Al11Si) is melted under normal atmosphere in an open crucible. The preform of Saffil, washed RF-grade Al_2O_3 fibres is fixed to the die by a high temperature "glue". This is to prevent the preform from leaving the die during excitation but also to control the melt flow through the preform, due to the low viscosity. This

arrangement is necessary or the melt will pass between the die and the preform. The form is made of steel and protected against chemical attacks from the melt by a thin layer of alumina. The vibration actuator is based on the elongation of magnetostrictive materials in a magnetic field. The actuator used is a result [13] of another research project of our department. Here a rod of Terfenol-D is used as the active part of the actuator. The actuator is a first generation prototype with a frequency range of $f=0-3$ kHz and maximum amplitude (A) of approximately $100 \mu\text{m}$. This actuator is continuously modified for improved performance, and $f=10$ kHz or higher is no problem for second generation actuators. To fulfill the infiltration a low pressure from a rotation pump is applied. Process description:

Figure 9. Test equipment for vibration excited low pressure casting, A) actuator, B) furnace, C) vacuum system, D) preform, E) crucible/melt.

1. The melt is heated to casting temperature, about 1100K.
2. The die is prepared with a preform (Saffil, infiltration depth max.20mm).
3. Oxide is removed mechanically from the surface of melt.
4. The die is lowered into the melt.
5. The temperature of the preform rises through the contact with the melt.
6. The actuator is activated.
7. A low pressure will be applied by opening the valve to the low pressure system.
8. Terminating infiltration by closing the valve and stop excitation.
9. The casting is taken out of the melt and cooled in air.

In these experiments only preforms with rather low vol. fraction (10% or less) fibre content were used. As a reference, castings without vibrational assistance were made under the same conditions as above.

Further testing When trying to infiltrate preforms with higher vol. fraction than 10% the initial test equipment failed due to the limits (~ 1 atmosphere) in applied pressure. Inspired by the Yang and Chung work [5] new testing equipment was constructed.

Figure 10. Principles of the "VHLI" process a) heating, b) melting, c) infiltration. "VHLI" equipment 1) closed die, 2) aluminium, 3) preform, 4) actuator.

In this process, "VHLI", a preform is placed in the lower part of a closable die with a piece of unmelted aluminium above the preform. The die is closed and evacuated by a vacuum pump during heating to about 50-100 degrees above liquidus. The aluminium melt "closes" the evacuated preform and thus enable infiltration, the die is vibration excited by a Terfenol actuator during application of an inert gas (Ar) pressure on top of the melt.

* Vibration assisted Hot Liquid Infiltration

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Results of initial tests Initial tests show that by adding vibrational energy it is possible to infiltrate a low fraction (6 vol.% fibres) Saffil preform at pressures as low as below 1 atmosphere. About 25 tests with the initial equipment were made, however, the best results show a great part of porosities making them unusable for more quantitative testing. Anyhow, these tests indicate a radical improvement in infiltration level compared to parallel tests without vibrational excitation where only partial infiltration occurred under these low pressures.

Figure 11. Typical results of initial testing, Saffil preform (6vol.% fibres), matrix: Al11Si, applied pressure $0.99 \cdot 10^5$ Pa a) without vibrational excitation b) vibr. excited, $f= 1$ kHz, $A= 0.1$ mm.

Results of further testing

The modified equipment, here called "VHLI", produces preform-based aluminium composites at

Figure 12. Light microscope study of Al11Si / 30 vol.% Saffil preform MMC produced by the "VHLI"-process. (magn. 1250x)

applied pressures in the range of 1-2 MPa depending on volume fraction of fibres and properties of the alloy. Dimensions of the preforms used are, diameter 85 mm and length 50 mm. Pictures above show that preforms containing 30 vol.% Saffil fibres can be well infiltrated at these low pressures by addition of vibrational energy.

6. DISCUSSION

The effects of vibrational assistance of the casting process in order to get infiltration and wetting of fibre preforms has been demonstrated for two simultaneous mechanisms working; variation of contact angle and the total kinematic pressure. The effect of these mechanisms depend strongly on the frequency used. On the basis of theoretical results (fig.8) we can assume the cooperation of these two effects, when the kinematic pressure is working in infiltration direction the contact angle will have high (bad) values and vice versa.

Another interesting mechanism is the surface behaviour regarding slot width and frequency (fig.3). At the same slot width a "low" frequency will cause a first mode oscillation, higher frequencies will, due to momentum of inertia, only physically move the fluid near the contact lines. The change in oscillation mode can also be studied in the diagram of total maximum kinematic pressure (fig.7). Maximum of kinematic pressure will occur when the surface oscillation is in "low" frequency mode (fig.3a), "high" (fig.3b) frequency mode reduces drastic the available kinematic pressure. According to this theoretical study, high frequencies (tens of kHz) is preferable for efficient infiltration in thin sections. These assumptions is consistent with the results

reported by Hitchcock et.al. for wetting of non wetting metals on rough ceramic substrates [1]. Vibrational assistance is a possible route to reduce the meniscus effects discussed by Young making complete infiltration of preform based composites thermodynamically impossible, without preform breakdown [8].

It is well known from practical experience, that the forced wetting induced by applied pressure is an almost irreversible process. The same phenomenon has also been found to be the case for vibrationally induced wetting [1].

Our hypothesis is therefore that the vibrational assistance acts like an additional pump for the infiltration process beside giving an improvement in wetting of the fibres.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Vibrational excitation of Saffil preforms improves infiltration by aluminium melt. Regarding the fine dimensions of the infiltration path inside a preform of this kind, theoretical studies in this work suggest the use of high frequencies (tens of kHz) to improve infiltration of thin sections in the preform by aluminium melt.

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